

Adducts of Some Unidentate Ligands with Tetrathiocyanato Zinc(II) Complexes

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TETRAHALO zinc(II) complexes and their reactions with different nitrogen ligands and a sulphur ligand have been reported¹⁻⁵ earlier. Ligands containing nitrogen as donor atom are bonded strongly to zinc(II) ion whereas sulphur coordination is not very strong. Penta-coordination in zinc(II) complexes was reported⁶ by us in an earlier communication. We report here some mixed ligand complexes obtained by reacting tetrathiocyanato zinc(II) compound with pyridine, 4-methyl pyridine, quinoline, iso-quinoline and thiourea. The compositions of the compounds actually isolated with some of their physico-chemical properties and analytical data are incorporated in Table 1.

at 27° with 10⁻³M solutions in acetone medium using a Toshnical Conductivity Bridge and a dip type cell. The infrared absorption spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in the region 4000-650 cm⁻¹ in Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP 200 double beam spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

When the tetrathiocyanato zinc(II) compound was reacted with ligands containing nitrogen or sulphur-donor atoms, reaction did take place forming entirely new compounds whose form, melting point and other characteristics were completely different from those of the starting materials. Analyses of the complexes for metal and thiocyanate reveal the formation of anionic complexes. In acetone medium, the Λ_M values for 2 : 1 electrolytes are usually round about 240 mhos and hence the values for Λ_M recorded in Table 1, show that these complexes are all 2 : 1 electrolytes and this observation is in conformity with their formulae.

Infrared Spectra :

The infrared frequencies of the thiocyanate groups in the complexes are listed in Table 2. Very sharp bands were observed near 2050 cm⁻¹ and sharp bands near 700 cm⁻¹ in all the cases. Terminal and bridging thiocyanate groups have been distinguished⁷

TABLE 1—M.P., ANALYSIS AND CONDUCTANCE OF TETRATHIOCYANATO ZINC (II) COMPLEXES

Complexes	Colour and form	M.P.°C	% of Zinc		% of SCN		Λ in mhos cm ² in acetone
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄]	White and micro crystalline	165	14.50	14.60	51.60	52.20	249
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ PY ₂]	Light yellow crystalline	118	10.50	10.77	38.00	38.47	220
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ Q]	-do-	160	11.00	11.30	40.90	40.41	230
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ (IQ) ₂]	White crystalline	109	9.10	9.24	33.80	33.00	225
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ (γ -pic) ₂]	Light yellowish crystalline	117	10.14	10.31	37.00	36.76	220
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ tu]	White crystalline	139	12.10	12.47	45.00	44.51	230

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal and thiocyanate following standard methods.

To the suspension of the tetramethyl ammonium tetrathiocyanato zinc(II) complex in ethanol, the ligand was added in 1 : 2 ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hrs, in the case of pyridine, 1 hr in case of 4-methyl pyridine and 2 hrs when the ligands were quinoline, iso-quinoline and thiourea. The resulting solution on cooling deposited crystalline complexes. They were filtered under suction washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuo.

All the complexes are fairly soluble in acetone. The conductance measurements were carried out

TABLE 2—INFRARED FREQUENCIES OF THE TETRATHIOCYANATO ZN(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	(Values in cm ⁻¹)	
	ν (C-N)	ν (C-S)
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄]	2050	700
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ PY ₂]	2060	718
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ Q]	2070	700
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ (IQ) ₂]	2060	710
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ tu]	2080	710
([Me ₄ N] ₂ [Zn(SCN) ₄ (γ -Pic) ₂]	2070	720

earlier and accordingly there are only terminal groups in the compounds reported here. Turco⁸ has distinguished between frequencies for M-SCN and M-NCS compound. The compounds reported here seem to possess M-NCS groups.

Further infrared spectra of the complexes show strong absorption bands of both the tetramethyl ammonium ion (745 cm⁻¹ and 970 cm⁻¹) and the ligands. The shifting of ligand absorption bands as seen in the infrared spectra of the complexes are indicative of definite metal ligand bonding.

The complexes having the formula [Me₄N]₂[Zn(SCN)₄L₂] where L is pyridine, 4-methyl pyridine and isoquinoline, seem to have hexa coordination, whereas the complexes [Me₄N]₂[Zn(SCN)₄L] where L = quinoline and thiourea are possibly penta coordinated. The exact coordination number can be established only by X-ray studies.

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Determination of Bismuth with Ammonium Phenylthiocarbamate as a Gravimetric Reagent

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MUSIL and Hass¹ studied the analytical characteristics of ammonium phenylthiocarbamate. The reagent has proved useful for many of the sulphide forming cations. The present report records the results of the gravimetric determination of bismuth(III) which is precipitated quantitatively in the pH range 0.8 to 6.3. Many a organic precipitant²⁻⁶ has been suggested for the gravimetric determination of bismuth. The use of the present reagent, however, is advantageous in certain respects. The reagent is very easily prepared, readily soluble in water and stable in the solid form. The bismuth complex is of definite composition and hence directly weighable. The complex, though unstable in the hot acid medium, is sufficiently granular and easily filterable at room temperature. In the presence of

EDTA the procedure is appreciably selective for the determination of bismuth. The following structure of the bismuth complex formed is suggested from its analytical data.

Experimental

Bismuth(III) Solution: Bismuth Nitrate pentahydrate (3.5262 g) of B.D.H. quality was dissolved in 1 litre of distilled water and acidified with nitric acid. Bismuth was determined as pyrogallate⁷. An aliquot was then suitably diluted to prepare a 0.1% solution of the metal.

Reagent Solution: Aqueous solution of the reagent (1.0%) prepared freshly was used for the determination.

Determination of Bismuth: Twenty five ml. of the bismuth solution was taken in a 500 ml beaker and diluted to about 130 ml. Ammonium Nitrate (2.5 g) and ten ml. of sodium potassium tartrate (10%) were added; the pH of the solution was adjusted between 5 to 6 by the addition of sodium acetate solution (10%). The reagent solution was then introduced dropwise with continuous stirring of the contents of the beaker. The yellow precipitate thus obtained was further stirred for about 10 mins. and then allowed to stand for half an hour. It was then filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G3), washed with water, and dried to a constant weight at 100° in about one and a quarter hours. The results are recorded in Table 1. The weight of the precipitate multiplied by 0.2754 gives the weight of bismuth.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF BISMUTH(III) IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS (25 mg of Bismuth taken for each determination)

Diverse ion	Added as	Amount added mg.	Bi Complex mg.	Bi found mg.	Error mg.
—	—	—	90.9	25.03	+0.03
—	—	—	90.7	24.98	-0.02
—	—	—	90.7	24.98	-0.02
—	—	—	90.8	25.00	0.00
K(I)	Nitrate	100	91.4	25.17	+0.17
Ca(II)	Chloride	100	91.8	25.27	+0.27
Be(II)	Nitrate	100	90.5	24.92	-0.08
Sr(II)	Nitrate	100	90.9	25.03	+0.03
Mg(II)	Nitrate	100	91.9	25.30	+0.30
Mn(II)	Chloride	100	91.4	25.17	+0.17
Zn(II)	Chloride	100	90.2	24.84	-0.16
Al(III)	Acetate	100	90.7	24.98	-0.02
Cr(III)	Acetate	100	90.7	24.98	-0.02
Fe(III)*	Ferric Alum	50	91.3	25.14	+0.14
Fe(II)*	Mohr's Salt	50	90.9	25.03	+0.03
Co(II)*	Nitrate	50	90.0	24.78	-0.22
Ni(II)*	Nitrate	50	90.9	25.03	+0.03
Pb(II)*	Nitrate	50	91.4	25.17	+0.17
Cd(II)*	Sulphate	50	91.4	25.17	+0.17
Zr(IV)	Nitrate	50	91.3	25.14	+0.14
Tungstate	Sodium	50	90.9	25.03	+0.03

* Masked with EDTA.